

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for VEGFR1 (UniProt ID: P17948) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Abstract

Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 1 (VEGFR1) is a tyrosine kinase receptor involved in cell migration, proliferation and angiogenesis. Here we have characterized thirteen VEGFR1 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P17948, *FLT1*, VEGFR1, Fms-like tyrosine kinase-1, Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

VEGFR1, encoded by the *FLT1* gene, is a member of the VEGF receptor family which belongs to the receptor type tyrosine kinase superfamily (1). Full-length VEGFR1 is a 150 kDa protein with seven Immunoglobulin-like domains in the extracellular region which are essential for ligands binding. The intracellular region contains the tyrosine kinase domain and an additional C-terminal tail crucial for signaling (2). This protein promotes cell migration in macrophages by activating PLC γ and PI3K pathways, and promotes macrophage proliferation through a PLC γ pathway (3). Though its role complex, VEGFR1 regulates angiogenesis (4). A soluble form secreted by endothelial cells contains only the Immunoglobulin-like domains 1–6 as well as 31 C-terminal amino acids (2). Soluble VEGFR1 promotes endothelial cell adhesion and migration (5). A decrease in VEGFR1 protein levels but an increase in the soluble form levels is observed in the brains of Alzheimer's disease patients (6).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (7). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (7). Here we characterized thirteen commercial VEGFR1 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, in western blot and immunoprecipitation, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of VEGFR1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (8) and in Table 4 of this data note (7).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (9, 10). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (11). The cell line A-375 expresses the *FLT1* transcript at $3.7 \log_2$ TPM+1, and the *FLT1* gene was CRISPR edited to generate a mixed KO population in A-375 (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the A-375 does not carry mutations in the *FLT1* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

We began by screening all thirteen VEGFR1 antibodies in western blot to assess their ability to detect secreted VEGFR1 in the culture medium of A-375 WT and *FLT1* KO cell lines. Proteins were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with VEGFR1 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1). Based on these results, five specific recombinant antibodies were selected for further analysis in cell lysates. However, intracellular VEGFR1 was found to be barely detectable in A-375 WT cells (Figure 2), and as a result, VEGFR1 antibodies were not pursued for immunofluorescence evaluation.

Next, we evaluated the ability of the thirteen antibodies to capture VEGFR1 from A-375 culture medium using the immunoprecipitation technique, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific VEGFR1 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 3).

In conclusion, we have screened thirteen VEGFR1 commercial antibodies by western blot and immunoprecipitation by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human A-375 WT and *FLT1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performanyce, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in these applications (11). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect VEGFR1 were identified in both applications. Researchers who wish to study VEGFR1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available VEGFR1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in VEGFR1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. VEGFR1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. Moreover, the same antibody clones are donated by 2-3 manufacturers (cross-licensed antibodies), effectively serving as replicates and enabling the validation of test reproducibility. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (7). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (12, 13). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

A-375 WT and *FLT1* KO cells were washed 3x with PBS 1x and starved for ~36 hrs. Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at 500 x *g* to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at 4500 x *g* to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were then concentrated by centrifuging at 4000 x *g* for 30 min using the Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024). Culture media were finally supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

For lysate preparation, cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix. Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot.

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 μ g of antibody to 500 μ l of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 87788 in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 μ l of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse and goat antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). NBP3-11864** was at an unknown concentration and therefore 5 μ l were tested in the IP. Tubes were rocked for ~ 1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

Culture medium from A-375 WT was collected as described in the western section above. 0.3 mL aliquots at 1.0 mg/mL of culture medium were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~ 1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 mL of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the VEGFR1 antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CRL-1619	CVCL_0132	A-375	WT
Knockout Cell Pool	-	-	A-375	<i>FLT1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the VEGFR1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab11934*	1049042-2	AB_2043171	monoclonal	EWF	mouse	0.50	Wb
Abcam	ab284963**	1081099-2	AB_3106904	recombinant mono	EPR21886-207	rabbit	1.02	Other
Abcam	ab285069**	1065464-3	AB_3106903	recombinant mono	EPR22248-131	rabbit	0.99	Other
Abcam	ab32152**	1015751-40	AB_778798	recombinant mono	Y103	rabbit	0.02	Wb, IP, IHC,
ABCD Antibodies	ABCD_AX014**	11/17/2023	AB_3076347	recombinant mono	N51/6.2	rabbit	0.04	-
ABCD Antibodies	ABCD_AX017**	11/10/2023	AB_3076346	recombinant mono	1G8	rabbit	0.04	-
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP61021_P050	QC31761-41444	AB_3073901	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NB100-527	A-7	AB_10003274	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-11864**	230299	AB_3076164	recombinant mono	SY09-09	rabbit	NA	Wb, IP, IF
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	AF321	AHT3422121	AB_355298	polyclonal	-	goat	0.20	Wb
GeneTex	GTX128969	41563	AB_2885853	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb,
Proteintech	13687-1-AP	00052344	AB_10644337	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32045**	YJ4089242	AB_2809339	recombinant mono	SY09-09	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence, *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Donkey Anti-Goat Antibody (H+L)	A15999	AB_2534673	polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Figure 1: VEGFR1 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

Figure 2: VEGFR1 antibody screening by western blot on lysate

A. Wb: AF321

A. Wb: AF321

B. Wb: ab284963**

Figure 2: VEGFR1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: VEGFR1 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium.

Culture media from A-375 WT and *FLT1* KO were collected, and 20 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated VEGFR1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO samples and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab11934* at 1/500, ab284963** at 1/1000, ab285069** at 1/1000, ab32152** at 1/1000, ABCD_AX014** at 1/40, ABCD_AX017** at 1/40, ARP61021 at 1/500, NB100-527 at 1/100, NBP3-11864** at 1/1000, AF321 at 1/2000, GTX128969 at 1/500, 13687-1-AP at 1/500, and MA5-32045** at 1/5000. Predicted band size: 150.7 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: VEGFR1 antibody screening by western blot on lysate.

Lysates from A-375 WT and *FLT1* KO were collected, and 20 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated VEGFR1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO samples and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions used: ab284963** at 1/1000, ab285069** at 1/1000, ab32152** at 1/1000, NBP3-11864** at 1/1000, and MA5-32045** at 1/5000. Predicted band size: 150.7 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 3: VEGFR1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium.

Culture medium was collected from A-375 WT, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.3 mg of protein and 2.0 µg of the indicated VEGFR1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with **A**) anti-VEGFR1 AF321 diluted at 1/200 or **B**) anti-VEGFR1 ab284963** at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=10% starting material; UB=10% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate, CRx=cross-reactivity. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.